

SOME NEW DEVELOPMENTS IN THE DESIGN OF STACKING SEQUENCES OF LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that the stacking sequence of the layers is of primary importance on the mechanical properties of a composite laminate. However, it has received little attention for the last years, in spite of the very small number of classical rules of design: the conditions of Werren and Norris for quasi-isotropic laminates and the condition of symmetry of the stacking sequence to eliminate the stretching-bending coupling constitute almost all the available rules; further, it should be emphasized that these conditions are usually misunderstood, as they are often considered as *necessary conditions*, whereas they are in fact only *sufficient conditions*.

In this paper, we used a method of polar representation of the anisotropic properties of two-dimensional systems to re-examine the effect of the stacking sequence on the stiffness properties of laminates. New methods and general rules are derived for the design of laminates with required stiffness properties for in-plane, bending and coupling. We also introduce new types of laminates such as *quasi-homogeneous* and *completely isotropic*. Incidentally, we point out that the classical condition of symmetry to suppress coupling is not necessary, by exhibiting some types of laminates without coupling, which are neither symmetric nor antisymmetric.

Further, using the polar representation method, we introduce a way to quantify the distance between two anisotropic elastic materials, which allows to define the concept of anisotropic materials *nearly equal*. From this concept, we can extend our rules and methods to the design of laminates with *nearly required properties*, and define new types of materials, such as *nearly quasi-homogeneous*, *nearly orthotropic*, *nearly isotropic* materials.

Examples, with graphical representations of the variation with the angle of the main equivalent engineering constants; are given to illustrate the various results.

INTRODUCTION

Knowing how to select the stacking sequence of a laminate, to fulfill some required properties, should constitute an essential objective in the design of laminated fibre reinforced plates. However, few papers have been published in this domain and they do not deal with all stiffness properties of laminates. For example, the conditions of Werren and Norris¹ for quasi-isotropic laminates are well-known and used, whereas nobody seems to look after the isotropy for bending. Another example is the condition of symmetry of the stacking sequence to eliminate the stretching-bending coupling, often misconceived till recently as a necessary condition: in spite of the work of Caprino and Crivelli-Visconti², generalized by Gunnink³, who presented a type of antisymmetric

laminate without coupling, and the work of Vong and Verchery⁴ who presented also two types of non-symmetric uncoupled laminates, people still has in mind that symmetry is the only solution to eliminate the stretching-bending coupling.

In this work, by the aid of a method of polar representation of the anisotropic properties of two-dimensional systems, we present in a lucid way the effect of the stacking sequence on the stiffness properties of laminates in stretching, bending and stretching-bending coupling. This method of polar representation was presented by Vong and Verchery⁴ and generalized results given by Tsai et al.^{7,8}. It was applied in the works of Kandil and Verchery^{5,6} and proves to be a very useful tool for aiding the design of laminates. It provides a clear understanding of stiffness properties of laminates, and generally of anisotropy.

THE METHOD OF POLAR REPRESENTATION

In this method of polar representation, a 4th rank tensor T_{ijkl} , such as the plane stress stiffness tensor of a lamina Q_{ijkl} , the stretching, bending and coupling tensors of a laminate, A_{ijkl} , D_{ijkl} and B_{ijkl} , is presented by six parameters $T_0, T_1, R_0, R_1, \theta_0$ and θ_1 . The first four and the difference of the two others are invariant in material rotation. This presentation appears in Eqs. 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{xxxx} &= T_0 + 2T_1 + R_0 \cos 4\theta_0 + 4R_1 \cos 2\theta_1 \\
 T_{yyyy} &= T_0 + 2T_1 + R_0 \cos 4\theta_0 - 4R_1 \cos 2\theta_1 \\
 T_{xyxy} &= T_0 - R_0 \cos 4\theta_0 \\
 T_{xxyy} &= R_0 \sin 4\theta_0 + 2R_1 \sin 2\theta_1 \\
 T_{yyxy} &= -R_0 \sin 4\theta_0 + 2R_1 \sin 2\theta_1 \\
 T_{xyyx} &= T_0 - R_0 \cos 4\theta_0 \\
 T_{yyxx} &= R_0 \sin 4\theta_0 + 2R_1 \sin 2\theta_1
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In other words, the tensor is represented by four polar components, two real T_0, T_1 and two complex $R_0 e^{4i\theta_0}, R_1 e^{2i\theta_1}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 8T_0 &= T_{xxxx} + T_{yyyy} - 2T_{xxyy} + 4T_{xyxy} \\
 8T_1 &= T_{xxxx} + T_{yyyy} + 2T_{xxyy} \\
 8R_0 e^{4i\theta_0} &= T_{xxxx} + T_{yyyy} - 2T_{xxyy} - 4T_{xyxy} + 4i(T_{xxyy} - T_{yyxx}) \\
 8R_1 e^{2i\theta_1} &= T_{xxxx} - T_{yyyy} + 2i(T_{xxyy} + T_{yyxx})
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

From this representation, we can separate the isotropic part of the material, which lies in the two real components (T_0, T_1). So, the material anisotropy can be defined through the other two complex components. Further, these quantities are closely related to the type of anisotropy for example, isotropy is equivalent to $R_0 = R_1 = 0$ and orthotropy to $\theta_0 = \theta_1 + k\pi/4$. With this representation, the prediction of the characteristics of laminates is simplified. For each type of laminate stiffness, stretching tensor **A**, bending tensor **D** or coupling tensor **B**, four polar components are introduced. Each component is the summation of the similar

quantity of the layers multiplied by the weighting factor of the classical theory of lamination. The details of this method is given in ⁵.

The present study is done for laminates of layers having the same material and thickness (Fig.1), which are the most used in industry. Following Tsai⁹ who introduced normalized stiffness matrices **A***, **B*** and **D*** with the same dimension as a Young's modulus, we use normalized polar components, so that comparison between different types of stiffness or between different laminates, regardless of thickness, can be done. Table 1 summarizes the twelve normalized polar components of a laminate as a function of the polar components of the basic layer, $m=0,1$ and $M=4,2$ respectively and k_p is the normalized weighting factor. In Table 1 and in the following, '-' stands for stretching, '~' for bending and '≃' for coupling.

Fig.1 Geometry of the laminate.

Table 1 summarizes the twelve normalized polar components of a laminate as a function of the polar components of the basic layer, $m=0,1$ and $M=4,2$ respectively and k_p is the normalized weighting factor. In Table 1 and in the following, '-' stands for stretching, '~' for bending and '≃' for coupling.

Table 1 Normalized polar components of a laminate in stretching, coupling and bending.

A*	$\bar{T}_m^* = T_m$ $\bar{R}_m^* e^{Mi\theta_m} = \frac{R_m}{N} \sum_{p=1}^N e^{Mi\theta_p}$	$\bar{k}_p = 1$ $\sum_{p=1}^N \bar{k}_p = N$
B*	$\tilde{T}_m^* = 0$ $\tilde{R}_m^* e^{Mi\theta_m} = \frac{R_m}{N^2} \sum_{p=1}^N \tilde{k}_p e^{Mi\theta_p}$	$\tilde{k}_p = \frac{h_p^2 - h_{p-1}^2}{h^2}$ $\sum_{p=1}^N \tilde{k}_p = 0$
D*	$\tilde{\tilde{T}}_m^* = T_m$ $\tilde{\tilde{R}}_m^* e^{Mi\theta_m} = \frac{4R_m}{N^3} \sum_{p=1}^N \tilde{\tilde{k}}_p e^{Mi\theta_p}$	$\tilde{\tilde{k}}_p = \frac{h_p^3 - h_{p-1}^3}{h^3}$ $\sum_{p=1}^N \tilde{\tilde{k}}_p = \frac{N^3}{4}$

As we see in Table 1, the isotropic parts (T_0 and T_1) in stretching and in bending are equal to those of the basic layer and are zero in coupling. So the difference between two stacking sequences of same material lies only in the anisotropic complex components. The six complex components of **A**, **B**, **D** are sufficient to describe the anisotropy of a general laminate. This has to be compared to the eighteen constants describing the behaviour of a general laminate with the classical representation of the laminated plate theory. The present method also describes the laminated plate theory but it uses fewer and more meaningful parameters to represent the anisotropy. Consequently, the anisotropy can be more easily controlled.

QUASI-HOMOGENEOUS LAMINATES

From the foregoing, we can conclude that a laminate has equal characteristics in stretching and in bending (same elastic constants) if the two normalized complex components are equal. We defined this type of

laminates as a **quasi-homogeneous** laminate. A rule for stacking sequences leading to this type of laminate can be obtained⁵ :

"A sufficient condition to get a quasi-homogeneous laminate is to choose an equal number of layers in each group of orientation, arranged so that the sum of their normalized weighting factors in bending are equal."

Some examples of this type of laminates are: the angle ply laminates $[\pm\theta]$, the antisymmetrical laminates $[\text{ABBABAAB}]$, which have the same properties of an angle ply laminate, and are in addition uncoupled and the laminates $[\text{AABBCCDDDCBCDDDBCAAABCBA}]_s$, which is completely isotropic⁴ in stretching as well as in bending, when the values of A, B, C and D satisfy the conditions of Werren and Norris.

STRETCHING-BENDING COUPLING

A general rule for stacking sequences of laminates to prevent coupling is formulated as follows⁵ :

"A sufficient condition to eliminate the stretching-bending coupling is that the sum of the normalized weighting factors of each group of orientation is equal to zero."

This condition is satisfied in the symmetric laminates as well as in the uncoupled laminates proposed in^{2,4}. Other examples of this type of laminates are: the laminates $[\text{ABBCAAB}]$, $[\text{ABCCBABACCAB}]$, $[\text{ABCCABBCA}]$, $[\text{ABCDCDABBCDADABC}]$ and $[\text{ABBBBCABAB}]$. The values of A, B, C and D stand for arbitrary orientations.

Further, an analytical study using the polar method of representation on thermal effect reveals (for laminates composed of the same basic layer) thermal coupling vanishes when the mechanical coupling is zero.

NEARLY EQUAL MATERIALS

From the four polar components of a tensor T_{ijkl} , we define a norm $N(\mathbf{T})$, equal to the square root of the weighted sum of the squares of the norms of the four polar components (the weights are related to the representation of general fourth rank tensors) :

$$N(\mathbf{T}) = \sqrt{(T_0)^2 + 2(T_1)^2 + |R_0 e^{4i\theta_0}|^2 + 4|R_1 e^{2i\theta_1}|^2} \quad (3)$$

This norm helps to quantify the difference between two anisotropic elastic materials. The distance between two tensors \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{T}' can be defined as follows :

$$\Delta N(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{T}') = \sqrt{(T_0 - T_0')^2 + 2(T_1 - T_1')^2 + |R_0 e^{4i\theta_0} - R_0' e^{4i\theta_0'}|^2 + 4|R_1 e^{2i\theta_1} - R_1' e^{2i\theta_1'}|^2}$$

Obviously if $\Delta N(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{T}')$ is equal to zero, then the two tensors \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{T}' are identical. When the ratio $\Delta N/N$ is small, i.e. less than a given small quantity ϵ (.01 or .001), the difference between the tensors \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{T}' is small and we designate such materials as **nearly equal** materials. In the following, we present some examples of materials having nearly equal properties.

1. Nearly Quasi-Homogeneous Material

The difference between the properties in stretching and in bending is quantified by the norm $\Delta N(\mathbf{A}^*, \mathbf{D}^*)$ which describe the distance between their

normalized stiffness tensors A^* and D^* . The material is said to be **nearly quasi-homogeneous** if $\Delta N(A^*, D^*)/N(A^*)$ is less than ϵ (.01 or .001). A graphical example is given in Fig. 2.

2. Nearly Orthotropic Material

In some cases of anisotropic material, the appearance of the terms 1112 and 2212 (16 and 26 in contracted notation) in the stiffness matrix, complicates the stress analysis calculation. So, it may be of interest to approximate the real material by an orthotropic material where these terms vanish (in the axes of orthotropy). A method to get such approximating material is derived from the condition of general orthotropy $\theta_0 = \theta_1 + k\pi/4$. The normalized components are compared and the real material is said to be **nearly orthotropic** if the ratio $\Delta N(T, T')/N(T)$ is less than ϵ . Fig. 3 gives a graphical example of such materials.

Fig. 2 Variation with angle of the in-plane and bending elastic constants for nearly quasi-homogeneous uncoupled laminates (values in GPa): $[30^\circ/-30^\circ/-30^\circ/30^\circ/30^\circ/-30^\circ]$ (T300/N5208).

Fig.3 In-plane elastic constants (variation with angle): comparison between a nearly orthotropic laminate $[15^\circ/-15^\circ/-15^\circ/30^\circ/15^\circ/15^\circ/-15^\circ]$ and its approximating orthotropic laminate: (T300/N5208, values in GPa).

3. Nearly Isotropic Material

When the load is not well anticipated, it is of interest to use isotropic laminates. Up till now, there is still no precise method to obtain a completely isotropic laminate, i.e. in stretching as well as in bending. So, laminate with nearly isotropic properties is the solution. These laminates can be obtained by a graphical method⁴ or repetition method⁵. We introduce the nondimensional parameters ρ_0 and ρ_1 calculated as follows:

$$\rho_m = \frac{R_m}{\sqrt{(T_0)^2 + 2(T_1)^2 + |R_0 e^{4i\theta_0}|^2 + 4|R_1 e^{2i\theta_1}|^2}}$$

$$\frac{\Delta N}{N} = \sqrt{\rho_0^2 + \rho_1^2}$$

Fig. 4 presents a graphical example of a **nearly isotropic** laminate of 18 layers, the anisotropy of which is 1.06% ($\Delta N/N = .0106$).

Fig. 4 Variation with angle of the in-plane and bending elastic constants for a nearly isotropic laminate : $[0^\circ/-60^\circ/60^\circ/60^\circ/0^\circ/60^\circ/60^\circ/0^\circ]$ (values in GPa, Glass/Epoxy).

CONCLUSION

Several applications of the method of polar representation were presented. We showed how the material anisotropy can be best controlled owing to the reduced number of significant parameters introduced by this method. We presented general rules of stacking sequence of laminates to get some fixed properties in stretching, bending and coupling. New types and concepts of material (quasi-homogeneous, complete isotropic, nearly quasi-homogeneous, nearly orthotropic and nearly isotropic materials), were introduced and illustrated.

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